

Assessing the Effects of a Precommitment Policy Applied During Peer Review

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Abstract

Improving journal policies and practices is hampered by a lack of experimentation and evidence. Implementing high-powered journal policy experiments to test solutions is difficult because of different journal management systems, ethical considerations for researcher privacy, and proprietary interests of publishers. In this article, we introduce a new policy and a new framework for experimental implementation at scale.

The policy, called “Registered Revisions”, triggers during traditional peer review when reviewers ask for additional data and/or analysis. Authors are asked to make a Revision Plan for how they will address these comments. If the Revision Plan and responses to standard questions are approved, editors agree to make an in-principle acceptance for publication decision. In other words, the article will be accepted as long as the Revision Plan is carried out as specified, regardless of the results. Registered Revisions enables authors and editors to gain experience of preregistering their methods without them having to proactively commit to a full, two-stage Registered Reports-style publication process.

The experimental framework is a meta experiment involving a collaboration of many journals. Each journal implements an experiment based on a shared protocol, logistical guidance, materials, and infrastructure. The journals can use and publish their experiments independently, and also contribute the data and findings to a prospective meta-analysis.

This approach presents a potential path forward for evidence-informed journal policy reform.

Background

Despite massive shifts in technology, science, and culture, the traditional peer review-based journal publication remains the overwhelmingly dominant mechanism for scientific dissemination and dialogue. Systemic issues with the reliability, utility, and incentives of scientific publication are intensifying. To counter this, we must engage in reform and rethinking of journal policy and implementation. One barrier to reform is a lack of experimentation in editorial policies that would provide evidence about what works and what does not when it comes to improving scientific publishing standards. The lack of evidence discourages implementation, which in turn contributes to a lack of evidence. We aim to break that cycle through a meta experiment exploring a policy called “Registered Revisions”.

Publication pre-commitment devices that have authors declare their intended methods and/or have journal acceptance on the basis of that plan may substantially reduce publication biases, prepublication biases (e.g., *p*-hacking and HARKing), and other questionable research practices. The two most commonly known precommitment devices are preregistration (Nosek et al. 2018; Sarafoglou et al. 2022) and Registered Reports (Chambers 2019; Scheel, Schijen, and Lakens 2021; Soderberg et al. 2021). In a preregistration, authors document a plan for the conduct of their research before research is carried out. In a Registered Report, authors enter into an agreement for publication based on review of their plan, regardless of their eventual

results. These devices work through enhanced planning, focus on the quality of methods before results, and provide opportunity for critical evaluation at the point at which it is most effective (i.e., before data gathering/analysis). However, evidence of impact of these devices is limited at this time, in part due to the difficulty of implementing robust causal impact designs for research and journal practice.

Researchers may face heightened pressure when addressing a request for additional analysis or data during traditional peer review. At this stage, authors have invested large amounts of resources and time with a particular journal, where rejection at this stage means starting the process over again or possibly not publishing the manuscript. It is also often unclear what peer reviewers are asking for and what they might accept should those data be collected. Reviewers may be focused more on results than the strength of methods, and authors may have increased incentives at this stage to engage in questionable research practices to push things over the finish line (Tennant and Ross-Hellauer 2020).

Registered Revisions is a new pre-commitment device that occurs during peer review. When reviewers ask for additional data and/or analysis, authors can propose and detail a Revision Plan of how those additional revisions will be performed. Reviewers and editors can make an in-principle acceptance for publication decision on the basis of this Revision Plan, regardless of what the results will be. Authors pre-commit to performing their Revision Plan for these new data/analysis requests, and editors/reviewers pre-commit to publishing the paper regardless of their results. In short, Registered *Revisions* incorporates ideas similar to Registered *Reports*, but applies to the traditional manuscript journal peer review process.

In theory, this style of review could reduce the impact of questionable research practices and publication-related biases, reduce uncertainty about peer review, and decrease review timelines through preventing multiple rounds of review. It also introduces new unfamiliar procedures and additional logistical steps to the manuscript review and revision workflow. At this time, we do not have evidence on this policy, as it has never before been implemented.

Developing useful experimental evidence for journal policies such as Registered Revisions is particularly challenging. Under standard approaches to large scale trials, this would typically require a relatively large sample size and a large consortium of journals. All journals would need to have tightly coordinated launch schedules and relatively homogeneous policy and experiment implementations to be part of the same study. In the end, participating journal editors' most direct career-sustaining reward would be the n^{th} author on a publication, reducing incentives to go out on a limb for a time consuming, difficult, and somewhat risky proposition. Different editors and institutions have a multitude of motivations. While many early adopters may be motivated to navigate these challenges due to a desire to improve scholarly communication systems, we are pairing this with more tangible - albeit nominal - incentives suitable for policy adoption at scale.

To tackle these issues, we are advancing a novel framework for evidence generation: a planned meta analysis consisting of individual journal-based experiments based on a study-in-a-kit developed for the purpose; i.e. a “meta experiment.”

This project has three main objectives:

- Test the efficiency and effectiveness of Registered Revisions
- Chart a pathway toward generating experimental evidence in journal policy
- Chart a pathway toward evidence-based journal reform

The first experimental component of this project, a pilot intended to navigate the logistics and infrastructure of both the policy and experimental design, is launching in *Evidence-Based Toxicology*.

Meta experiment

The Center for Open Science (COS) is leading a set of journal-run randomized experiments on Registered Revisions (Center for Open Science 2024; Haber et al. 2023). These are centrally coordinated by COS, including a shared overall protocol and data collection infrastructure, while the individual journals themselves decide the specifics of how they run the trial. These individual journal-run experiments then contribute to a meta-analysis, synthesizing the individual experiments into a well-powered, reasonably-generalizable pool of study results.

This many-study approach helps foster:

- A feasible approach to policy implementation experiments that would otherwise require an unrealistic degree of coordination and editorial homogeneity
- Minimum workload for journal-based partners
- A more realistic roll-out of the Registered Revisions policy, as each journal or journal group will be implementing it in their own unique way
- Sharing of experience and guidance across journal editorial teams
- A guarantee that small trials are part of a larger evidence base, preventing research waste

Journal and Journal Consortia	COS Provides
Journals have full ownership of their RCT. Each RCT is specific to the journals' individual needs and preferences for: <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Specific intervention policy design● Schedule/timelines● Outcomes measured	Boilerplate study design, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Protocol● Data collection and curation● Data analysis design and code● Administrative infrastructure● Institutional review board pathway and materials● Centralized communication● Implementation, design, and logistical support

The journals running the individual experiments fully own their own data and publications resulting from the trial, and are expected to be the authors on any publications resulting from

their experiments. The journal implementation team will also be co-authors on the COS-led meta-analysis. COS provides study design and implementation support, and the editorial team implements their own logistical procedures for the design.

Individual randomized journal studies design overview

Consenting authors are eligible to participate in the trial if they have received peer-review requests for new data and/or new analysis as part of the revise-and-resubmit process. Eligible participants are randomized to one of two trial arms, a Registered Revisions arm and a standard procedures arm.

If Registered Revisions arm:

- Author team drafts a Revision Plan to describe procedures for new data analysis and outcomes, before collecting new data
- Editors and/or peer reviewers review the Revision Plan and (if/when approved) issue an In-Principle Acceptance regardless of the results.
- Journal team tracks outcomes and implements any data collection

If Standard procedures arm:

- Manuscript undergoes standard procedures for their journal

Figure 1: Trial workflow

The expected workflow for both the Registered Revisions policy and the trial itself are expected to vary substantially between fields and journals. We have developed and are testing an infrastructure and workflow that we believe to be reasonably generalizable and adaptable to a wide range of scenarios. A general diagram of the workflow for Registered Revisions is provided in Figure 1. We have also provided a

full example workflow hosted on an Open Science Framework (OSF) project for this study (Haber et al. 2023). **This includes a procedural reference, templates and instructions for communication with and between authors and peer reviewers, and data entry infrastructure. Note that these are for demonstration purposes only at this time.**

Data and outcomes

Data will be primarily collected through the recording of event dates (e.g., peer review, author revision submissions, editorial decision dates), with additional information being collected by survey.

There are three key categories of outcomes in this trial: (1) procedural outcomes with the peer review process itself, (2) research reliability outcomes related to the outputs of the manuscripts reviewed, and (3) perceptual outcomes having to do with how authors, reviewers, and editors experience the policy and trial. Among those, the procedural outcomes are our primary outcomes for both feasibility and interpretability. Time to event outcomes are continuous outcomes that differ for each submission, and are relatively straightforward to interpret, particularly from a casual perspective. Process outcomes are also typically the primary interest of journals and publishers, who may be concerned about workloads or procedural backlogs.

While research reliability outcomes are a strong interest, indicators of it (e.g., an increase in the proportion of null results) are binary, likely to be relatively small differences between arms, and conditional on the downstream causal effects of the trial arm. This makes them comparatively less powered and more difficult to measure and interpret. Finally, the perceptual outcomes will provide key subjective data that will inform implementability at scale largely through qualitative assessment.

The expected outcomes are a combination of process outcomes (e.g., time to reaching final decisions, acceptance/rejection rates), research outcomes (e.g., statistical significance, effect sizes), and satisfaction outcomes (e.g., how researchers and editors feel about the process). The primary outcomes for this project are time to event, particularly from peer review to final outcomes (both acceptance and rejection). Journals are free to choose which and how they report outcomes, with the understanding that the data generated in their trials will also be used in the main meta-analysis.

Pathfinder pilot

This project encompasses several aspects that are innovations on the status quo: 1) the Registered Revisions policy, 2) conducting a randomized experiment within a journal, and 3) the semi-centralized prospective meta analysis. Given the novelty of this approach, we are conducting a pathfinder pilot study. This pathfinder pilot consists of 5-10 journals on a rolling basis, including *Evidence Based Toxicology*, collectively and individually charting a path toward feasible implementation at scale.

In this pathfinder pilot, we are experimenting with how to conduct randomized trials of review policy as well as how to implement the policy itself. That includes developing and testing participant tracking and data collection infrastructure, informed consent processes, IRB approvals, and instructional materials. Most importantly, the pathfinder pilot will yield actual real-world implementation experience which will inform and guide both the main phase of this project and other potential evidence-generation efforts to come.

Summary

Registered Revisions is an incremental policy reform rather than a comprehensive fix to the shortcomings of our current publication system; it occurs during the traditional peer review process, does not require new publication formats or a major change in the conduct of research practice, requires relatively little change to new processes and procedures, and allows for variation in how requests for new additional data or analysis occur at different journals. Takeup of precommitment devices like preregistration and Registered Reports is hampered by requiring the researchers to know what these devices are, to be willing to change their behaviors, and be willing to take risks on something new. Registered Revisions introduces precommitment devices during the course of standard journal review, shifting the impetus for change to journals. The policy provides a restructuring of the revision process that allows researchers to engage in precommitment in a low-risk, capacity-efficient way. We hope it provides a stepping stone toward engagement in more comprehensive reforms and formats, such as Registered Reports. Most importantly, we believe that we have created a way to find out if and how well preregistration works on a variety of dimensions, ranging from research burden, satisfaction, and the quality and reliability of subsequent research.

Many of the early pathfinder journal partners are based in the social sciences, biology, and medicine, in large part due to direct human impact and having communities that are relatively actively engaged in open science and institutional reform (Ferguson et al. 2023; Silverstein et al. 2024; Hair et al. 2019; Cobo et al. 2011). *Evidence Based Toxicology* is among the two first pilots launched, and has had a key role in co-designing and iterating on the implementation and logistical design of this project.

This project hinges on a new policy, a new framework for evidence generation, and a new approach to experimentation. In combination, this represents a potential way forward for evidence based journal reform through evidence generation. As with any new policy,, at this time we simply do not know how it will work in practice. To break the there-is-no-evidence to there-is-no-change to there-is-no-evidence cycle, we are starting with change into unknown and unknowable territory through experimenting with Registered Revisions.

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Works cited

- Center for Open Science. 2024. "Impact of Registered Revisions." Registered Revisions Project. 2024. <https://www.cos.io/r3ct/registered-revisions>.
- Chambers, Chris. 2019. "The Registered Reports Revolution Lessons in Cultural Reform." *Significance* 16 (4): 23–27. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1740-9713.2019.01299.x>.
- Cobo, E, J Cortés, JM Ribera, F Cardellach, A Selva-O'Callaghan, B Kostov, L García, et al. 2011. "Effect of Using Reporting Guidelines during Peer Review on Quality of Final Manuscripts Submitted to a Biomedical Journal: Masked Randomised Trial." *BMJ (Clinical Research Ed.)* 343 (November):d6783. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.d6783>.
- Ferguson, Joel, Rebecca Littman, Garret Christensen, Elizabeth Levy Paluck, Nicholas Swanson, Zenan Wang, Edward Miguel, David Birke, and John-Henry Pezzuto. 2023. "Survey of Open Science Practices and Attitudes in the Social Sciences." *Nature Communications* 14 (1): 5401. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-41111-1>.
- Haber, Noah, Timothy M. Errington, Macie Daley, and Brian A. Nosek. 2023. "COS Registered Revisions Meta Experiment." <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/TSHQU>.
- Hair, Kaitlyn, Malcolm R. Macleod, Emily S. Sena, Emily S. Sena, Kaitlyn Hair, Malcolm R. Macleod, David Howells, et al. 2019. "A Randomised Controlled Trial of an Intervention to Improve Compliance with the ARRIVE Guidelines (IICARus)." *Research Integrity and Peer Review* 4 (1): 12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41073-019-0069-3>.
- Nosek, Brian A., Charles R. Ebersole, Alexander C. DeHaven, and David T. Mellor. 2018. "The Preregistration Revolution." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 115 (11): 2600–2606. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1708274114>.
- Sarafoglou, Alexandra, Marton Kovacs, Bence Bakos, Eric-Jan Wagenmakers, and Balazs Aczel. 2022. "A Survey on How Preregistration Affects the Research Workflow: Better Science but More Work." *Royal Society Open Science* 9 (7): 211997. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.211997>.
- Scheel, Anne M., Mitchell R. M. J. Schijen, and Daniël Lakens. 2021. "An Excess of Positive Results: Comparing the Standard Psychology Literature With Registered Reports." *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science* 4 (2): 25152459211007467. <https://doi.org/10.1177/25152459211007467>.
- Silverstein, Priya, Colin Elman, Amanda Montoya, Barbara McGillivray, Charlotte R. Pennington, Chase H. Harrison, Crystal N. Steltenpohl, et al. 2024. "A Guide for Social Science Journal Editors on Easing into Open Science." *Research Integrity and Peer Review* 9 (1): 2. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41073-023-00141-5>.
- Soderberg, Courtney K., Timothy M. Errington, Sarah R. Schiavone, Julia Bottesini, Felix Singleton Thorn, Simine Vazire, Kevin M. Esterling, and Brian A. Nosek. 2021. "Initial Evidence of Research Quality of Registered Reports Compared with the Standard Publishing Model." *Nature Human Behaviour* 5 (8): 990–97. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-021-01142-4>.
- Tennant, Jonathan P., and Tony Ross-Hellauer. 2020. "The Limitations to Our Understanding of Peer Review." *Research Integrity and Peer Review* 5 (1): 6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41073-020-00092-1>.